

SIMLE SENTENCES EXPRESSING CONDITIONAL RESULT RELATIONSHIPS AND WAYS OF THEIR TRANSLATION

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Nowadays the English language is taught as a compulsory subject in all institutions in Uzbekistan. Teaching and learning English has some specific peculiarities and is required a special teaching program and methodology. Studying of scientific-methodological sources, analyzing of current curriculums and texts-books show that the English language Plays a great role for students in being a high qualified specialist. But at present the level of teaching and learning the English language doesn't correspond to modern requirements. It is important to notice that the cause of such negative result English teachers don't have enough professional skills and modern requirements aren't taken into account in current curriculums, text-books and

methodological appliances, modern pedagogical technologies aren't used in teaching foreign languages as well. The article is devoted to the problem of Differentiated Strategies in teaching English which puts students at the center of teaching and learning. [1]

It is a common-sense, as well as research-based, approach to meeting the diverse needs of learners while promoting equity and excellence. It promotes a curriculum centered on critical thinking and acknowledges the uniqueness of each learner. In an attempt to enhance students' learning, and maximize their achievement, numerous schools are implementing differentiated instruction. A process to approach teaching and learning for students of differing abilities in the same class. The intent is to maximize each student's growth and individual success by meeting each student where he or she rather than expecting students to modify themselves for the curriculum. Maximizing the conceptual understanding of the material taught is the goal of any educator. With the current diversity inside classrooms, it is almost impossible for teachers to challenge all their students in the same class unless they reform the curriculum in a way to reach all students. Differentiating instruction is not a new idea, but the issue has been gaining an ever-higher profile for English teachers in recent years. More and more, educational systems and parents are expecting the teacher to be aware of what each individual student-whether a struggling student, an average student, or a gifted student-needs and plan instruction to take those needs into account [2].

Differentiated instruction (DI) is nothing new and is believed to be an effective research-based strategy to cater for learner diversity.

Differentiation involves finding multiple ways to structure a lesson so that each student is provided with an opportunity to work at a moderately challenging level. Previous studies, however, found that teachers were not well prepared and insufficiently equipped with skills and knowledge about DI. Differentiated instruction (DI) is regarded as the most effective strategy to cater for learner diversity. [3]

We are situated at a moment in our national educational history when we have the opportunity to learn anew how to craft classrooms in which each student has access to high quality knowledge, understanding, and skill.

There are three significant implications contained in this opportunity.

First, we can no longer accept classrooms that relegate some students to low level learning. [4] Second, in addition to providing rich, powerful, high quality curriculum for all learners, we must ensure instructional support

systems that make it possible for each learner to take advantage of what a high quality curriculum has to offer. Third, we must learn how to establish the goal of ensuring that each student grows as much as he or she can grow at a given time and how to acknowledge the growth appropriately when it occurs. To succeed in establishing classrooms where all students work with ideas and skills that equip them for a future of continued learning, to provide support systems that promote systematic development of the individual, and to settle for nothing less than the best a student has to offer is to achieve classrooms that represent both equity and excellence. [5]

Here is a summary of the successes and challenges researchers experienced while working with student in a differentiated classroom environment.

Successes

- 1) Increased student motivation in approaching academic tasks;
- 2) Improved study habits and problem solving skills for students;
- 3) Students recognized the value of paying attention to different learning styles and the need to apply this approach to their classroom teaching during practicum;
- 4) Bringing the topics of curriculum studies to life; increased meaning and understanding by making connections to real life classroom and world situations;
- 5) Group cooperation and collaboration;
- 6) Greater involvement, understanding and improved academic performance by all students;
- 7) Building improved relationships between students and instructors. [6]

Challenges

- 1) A very time consuming exercise with long hours of planning, organizing and scheduling individuals and groups in a large class setting ;
- 2) Difficult to cater to individual needs and preferences especially those individuals who prefer to work alone;
- 3) The examination culture which has pervaded teacher education institutions seemed to have great impact.[7]

Some students questioned the fairness of the process when assessments were differentiated. Different studies showed that DI had positive impacts on student learning in different levels of schooling. Effectiveness of DI usage was evidenced in different subject disciplines. Although there is a strong need for teachers who can ‘proactively respond to and reach the varied needs of diverse student populations, grouped heterogeneously, at a high-level’ disappointingly, little differentiation practice or negative effects on teachers occur in curriculum and instruction in reality. It was also noted that DI strategies were used more frequently to meet the needs of at-risk or struggling students rather than academically advanced students within a mixed-ability classroom. Based on an extensive literature about DI, four critical factors influencing the implementation of DI in schools are identified: teacher preparation, teaching beliefs, school support, and team collaboration.

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